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АКАДЕМИЯСИ МИНТАҚАВИЙ БЎЛИМИ
ХОРАЗМ МАЪМУН АКАДЕМИЯСИ**

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АКАДЕМИЯСИ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

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vaqtning o'zida birlashgandan ko'ra ko'proq bo'lingan ikki kishi bo'lishiga to'g'ri keladi. Uilyam Krimsvort obrazi ham ayollik, ham erkaklik xususiyatlarini birlashtiradi va shunga mos ravishda ikkita funksiyani bajaradi: Frensisning oshig'i va eri sifatida u gender munosabatlarga erkak nuqtai nazarini ifodalaydi, ziddiyatli xarakter egasi sifatida esa ayol shaxsi va uning jamiyatdagi mavqei haqidagi ijodkorning qarashlarini yetkazish vositasi bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Fikrimizcha, Sh.Bronte keyingi romanlarida, ayniqsa «O'qituvchi» dagi mavzuning o'ziga xos davomi bo'lgan «Shaharcha»da ko'p qirrali va ziddiyatli «ayol» tajribasini ancha ishonarli tarzda taqdim etadi. Biroq, uning birinchi asarida gender muammolari talqini mavjud bo'lib, u yozuvchining keyingi barcha romanlarda o'z aksini topadi.

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INTERPRETATION OF SOCIO-COMMUNICATIVE AND LINGUA-CULTURAL ASPECTS IN TRANSLATOR'S THINKING

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Annotatsiya. *Tarjimada lingvistik va madaniy jihatlardan to'g'ri foydalanish tarjima sohasidagi muhim masalalardan biridir. Muayyan xalq madaniyati va millat tafakkurini chuqur bilmay turib, tilni yaxshi o'zlashtirmasdan tarjimon tarjimada badiiy til vositalarini, ijtimoiy-kommunikativ va lingvo-madaniy jihatlarni to'g'ri tanlay olmaydi va natijada tarjima to'g'ri va sifatli bo'lmaydi. Ushbu maqolada tarjimon tafakkurining ijtimoiy-kommunikativ va lingvo-madaniy jihatlari tarjima sifatini oshirish me'yorlariga muvofiq talqin qilish muhokama qilinadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *tarjima, tarjimaning ijtimoiy-kommunikativ jihatlari, tarjimaning lingvo-madaniy jihatlari, tarjimon tafakkuri.*

Аннотация. *Правильное использование языковых и культурных аспектов в переводе является одним из важных вопросов в области перевода. Без глубоких знаний культуры и ассоциативного мышления конкретного народа и без хорошего владения языком переводчик не может правильно выбирать средства художественного языка и социально-коммуникативные и лингвокультурологические аспекты в переводе и, как следствие, перевод не будет правильным и эффективным. В данной статье рассматривается интерпретация социально-коммуникативных и лингвокультурологических аспектов мышления переводчика в соответствии с нормами повышения качества перевода.*

Ключевые слова: *перевод, социально-коммуникативные аспекты перевода, лингвокультурологические аспекты перевода, переводческое мышление.*

Abstract. *The correct use of linguistic and cultural aspects in translation is one of the important issues in the field of translation. Without having a deep knowledge of the culture and associative thinking of a particular nation and without a good mastery of the language, the translator cannot choose the tools of the artistic language correctly and socio-communicative and lingua-cultural aspects in translation and as a result, the translation will not be correct and effective. This article discusses the interpretation of socio-communicative and lingua-cultural aspects of translator's thinking in accordance with the norms for improving the quality of translation.*

Key words: *translation, socio-communicative aspects of translation, lingua-cultural aspects of translation, translator's thinking.*

Due to the rapid development of modern globalization, the expansion of international relations between countries, the development of science and technology and continuous flow of scientific and technical information increased the need for high-qualified translators in all fields who must have wealth of knowledge in various fields and consider linguistic and cultural aspects of the language appropriately in translation. This principle implies the ability of the translator to develop the aptitude to use the knowledge in the process of translating materials of various genres. In addition, translator should be able to perceive the difference between cultures, understand the mentality of the people in the original language of the text. Being able to use lexical, grammatical, and stylistic methods in accordance with translation norms improves the quality of translation.

A translator who works with literary translation is required not only to master a foreign language, but also to know the history and culture of the target language, knowledge of international cultural relations, the field of psychology, and the history of peoples and religions. However, in order to be able to express culture in the form of semantics in linguistic units, it is important to have a high level of knowledge in the areas listed above. Therefore, in the thorough study of a foreign language, it is necessary to attach serious importance to the teaching of the methodology, culture, literature, country studies, the theory and practice of oral and written translation, as well as the sciences of professional learning of this language. A translator is required to be not only a linguist, but also a literary and ethnologist. Without having a deep knowledge of the culture and associative thinking of a particular nation and without a good mastery of the language, the translator cannot choose the tools of the artistic language correctly, without socio-communicative and lingua-cultural aspects, and as a result, the translation will not be correct and effective. In this sense, translator needs such skills, including choosing words, the correct reflection of the spirit of the time through language units, to reach the level of being able to accept and evaluate written sources, to approach the historical and cultural heritage with respect and attention, be able to distinguish information from a social and cultural point of view, to form the ability to use logical sequences in the implementation of literary translation, to translate without destroying the essence of the original text being able to reveal correctly will rise to the professional level.

Translators differ in style, each translator has his own individual style that is different from others, and different stylistic directions are manifested in translation. It requires the translator to find a style key that matches the original. Finding the key to the appropriate style in translation depends on the ability to determine the appropriate connection between the writing style of the work, the idea and the author's worldview, and the ability to determine the characteristics of the rhythm, melody, syntactic style and series of images. The translator must recreate the unity of form and content in a copy similar to the original. It is through translation that lingua-cultural barriers can be overcome. Therefore, translation is one of the most important mediators between societies and cultures.

Hence, every genre of translation has its own complexities. Let's analyze interpretation of humor in translation in terms of socio-communicative and lingua-cultural aspects of translator's thinking. Humor is a nationality characteristic of all nations. Humor is one of the basis of socio-communicative and lingua-cultural aspects of translator's thinking. Every nation has its own values and traditions. It has its own way of thinking, which is different from other nations. Now, we can compare Uzbek and English jokes. British humor is very unique. Many people cannot digest English humor. Therefore, the translator should approach the translation process carefully. It depends on the skill of the translator that the reader, who is reading the translated text, even if he is encountering the English culture for the first time, will be able to find the right place where he should be able to laugh and feel the humor there. The skill of the translator depends on his knowledge of English culture and lifestyle. Humor is an integral part of human life. It helps both adults and children learn and remember subjects easily. In addition, it ensures that people quickly get along with each other and assimilate into society in a short time. It is very difficult for a person without a sense of humor to integrate into society. For example, English people often use weather-related situations in jokes. However, it may be incomprehensible to us. It is natural that we cannot fit it into our imagination. Nevertheless, just as pilaf is considered an indispensable daily dish of the Uzbek people, jokes about the weather are also a small aspect of everyday life for the British. The language is a unique system of tools in the interaction of the nation. One of the important features of understanding English humor is the English language itself. Translating English jokes is difficult task. In this case, it is necessary not only to study the English language deeply and extremely carefully, but also to master the finer points of our native language and be able to use it appropriately in the process of translation. Not only the knowledge of the language, but also our familiarity with the culture of the English people will come in handy. If we know the mentality of those people well, we will be able to convey humor beautifully in translation. In this case, translators should focus on determining the extent of national features reflected in the culture related to specific historical, geographical, onomastic, and other concepts and views are absorbed into the spirit of the translation. Since the most important feature of translation is nationality, it means that preserving nationality in translation, in other words, re-creating it, is the main indicator and main factor of successful translation.

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